

**Scientific and theoretical foundations of cooperative pedagogy and its role in the
modern education system****BOBOEYEVA SABINAKHAN LAZIZ KIZI**
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One of the important requirements for today's teachers and educators, especially professors working in higher education institutions, is to teach young people to think independently by deeply understanding and applying innovations in the field of education. Knowing the essence and ideas of cooperative pedagogy is also one of these requirements.

Keywords: Higher education, innovation, technology, cooperative pedagogy, humanity, joint activity, team, small group, emotional-psychological environment.

Introduction. Article 36 of the Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On Education", approved on September 23, 2020, states: "Experimental and innovative activities in the field of education are carried out with the aim of modernizing education and are aimed at developing new educational technologies and resources, testing them and introducing them into the educational process"[1].

And we will achieve this through innovations in education. One of the important requirements for teachers and educators is to teach young people to think independently through a deep understanding and application of innovations in the field of education. Developing practical foundations for the use of modern pedagogical and innovative technologies in the organization of the educational process and effective ways to use them is one of the urgent issues facing the education system.

In implementing these works, it is of particular importance that continuing education, especially higher education institutions and professors working in them have sufficient professional qualifications, work on themselves, and be aware of advanced pedagogical practices. In this regard, it is important to know and use the essence and ideas of cooperative pedagogy.

The ideas of cooperative pedagogy are today embedded in the content of pedagogical technologies and form the basis of the “21st Century Education Concept”. Cooperative pedagogy is integral and interconnected with humanistic pedagogy. In the educational system of developed countries, cooperative pedagogy has long been used. Methodology and object of the study. The idea of cooperative pedagogy was first put forward by D. Dewey in the 1920s. However, the methodological description of this pedagogy was published in the press in different countries of the world in the late 70s and early 80s, in Russia, Great Britain, Canada, West Germany, Austria, the Netherlands, Japan, and Israel.

Various aspects of cooperative pedagogy can also be seen in the pedagogical theories of K.D. Ushinsky, N.P. Pirogov, L.N. Tolstoy, S.T. Sratsky, V.A. Sukhomlinsky, A.S. Makarenko, J.J. Russo, Y. Korczak, K. Rogers, E. Berne. Although the representatives of this direction had different views on education, their main goal was to “humanize” the education system. In the research of Simon Lvovich Soloveitchik, one of the founders of the idea of cooperative pedagogy, a new approach to the issue of upbringing was highlighted, in which upbringing began to be expressed not as some kind of influence of the educator on the child, but as an open relationship between the teacher and the student. The ideas of cooperative pedagogy were also reflected in the theories of Amonashvili Shalva Aleksandrovich, Shatalov Viktor Fedorovich, Lisenkova Sofya Nikolayevna and others.

The first meeting of pedagogical innovators took place in October 1986 in the village of Peredelkina near Moscow. As a result of the meeting, “Theses of cooperative pedagogy” was published in the newspaper “Uchitelskaya” on October 18, 1986. Their second meeting took place in Georgia in 1987. At this meeting, “Ways and directions of democratization of education” were determined. As a result, theses on the topic “Democratization of the individual” were published in the newspaper “Uchitelskaya”. The main ideas of cooperative pedagogy were later proposed and methodologically described by American scientists George Aronson (1978), Rogers and David Johnson (1987), Robert Slavin (1990), and the Israeli scientist Shlomo Sharan (1988).

We can also see cooperative activities in the studies of foreign scientists, where “cooperation” and “competition” are recognized as the goals of student activity. D.B. Miller notes that in a cooperative situation, there is a common goal, and all students divided into groups are given tasks, while in a competitive situation, each member of the group is required to individually achieve the set goal in a holistic manner [4]. M.A. May, L.U. Duba also note the existence of a common goal shared between its participants in the process of cooperation and the establishment of friendly relations between them [4]

Foreign studies pay special attention to revealing the possibilities of the group form of collaborative learning. In particular, D.V. Johnson, R.T. Johnson proposed combining individual educational and cognitive activities of students with joint work in small groups [6]. D. De Vries (D. DeVries) and K. Edwards (K. Edwards) [5] described game methods for organizing a group form of organizing joint activities of students in educational and cognitive activities.

In accordance with the ideas of E. Aronson, in the process of developing students' cooperation in educational and cognitive activities, the organization of their interaction in the group requires that each participant initially work on a certain part of the general task, explain the studied material to each other and help other participants in the group to fulfill their share of the task, and ultimately allow students to achieve the set goal.

Research results and discussion. Cooperative pedagogy is close to “creative pedagogy” in

terms of its “creativity” nature. According to pedagogical innovators, cooperative pedagogy should accept any child as he is. In this case, the teacher helps the child to maintain his individuality and awakens the motivation for his mental and moral development.

The following can be cited as the main ideas of cooperative pedagogy:

- teaching the child in the zone of proximal development:
- teaching without coercion:
- teaching based on basic words, schemes, symbols:
- the idea of progression: - the idea of large blocks:
- the idea of free choice:
- the idea of dialogic thinking:
- the idea of the intellectual environment of the classroom:
- the idea of joint activity of students and teachers:
- the idea of voluntary activity in free time.

Cooperative educational technology aims to form a worldview in students based on the development of intellectual, spiritual-moral and physical abilities, interests, and motivations. Cooperative pedagogy is an independent pedagogical concept, the main result of which is the achievement of the intended goal in the cooperation of the student (pupil) and the teacher. Education, which involves the joint mastery of knowledge in pairs, mutual development, the joint organization of the relationship "student-student (s)", "pedagogue-student (s)", involves the implementation of tasks in small groups or pairs, together, in mutual cooperation.

"Cooperative pedagogy" is considered a technology of education according to its level of application: general pedagogical, according to its philosophical foundations: humanistic, according to its approach to the child: personal-humanistic, subject-subject (cooperation) and according to the application of methods: problem-search, creative, dialogic, game-based.

As principles of cooperative educational technology:

- mutual unity of members of pairs and small groups;
- responsibility of each member for personal and group success in pairs and small groups;
- organization of cooperative learning activities in small groups;
- we can indicate a general assessment of group and team work.

As signs of cooperative educational technology, we can indicate the following:

- attention to the student's personality, individuality;
- development of independent and critical thinking in students;
- ensuring the emergence of a positive attitude towards the teacher and peers;
- developing cultural communication skills in students;
- creating an environment based on cooperation and mutual equality.

When using collaborative learning technology, students learn in a team; in a small group; in pairs.

Conclusion: Pedagogical cooperation contributes to the formation and manifestation of new

qualitative changes in the activities of the subjects of the educational process. An important aspect of pedagogical cooperation is that it serves to harmonize the activities of the subjects of the educational process in a certain way. In the process of pedagogical cooperation, the activities of the teacher and the student (pupil) are harmonized, acquire a creative character, which requires taking into account each specific aspect of the activities of the subjects of the educational process. Cooperation in the "teacher-student" relationship is organized on the basis of a joint analysis of the course and results of this activity, sincerity to each other in the spiritual world, strong mutual understanding, and the idea of joint developmental activity of adults and children. In the pedagogical process in traditional education, the participation of the teacher as a subject and the student as an object is replaced by the participation of the student as a subject of activity. The "teacher-student" relationship is realized in such types of cooperation as (co-participation, co-care, co-creation, co-management) adopted in

Improving the educational process in higher education on the basis of cooperative pedagogy is an activity aimed at introducing certain changes in the practice of educational institutions, the effectiveness of which is determined by the enrichment and improvement of the quality of educational content, the increase in the level of knowledge, skills and qualifications of students, their possession of high spiritual and moral qualities, the establishment of active cooperation between teachers and students in the educational process.

We paid attention to the following criteria and indicators of improving the educational process on the basis of cooperative pedagogy:

- the presence of a dialogical characteristic of mutual joint activity in the educational process (communicative attitudes of subjects in the process of dialogical relations);
- the generality of the value-oriented attitude of subjects in the educational process (mutual respect, mutual trust, mutual understanding, value orientation of subjects to joint activities in a conscious sense of responsibility);
- the consistency of the joint actions of subjects (the ability to jointly set a goal, plan ways to achieve it,
- implement the established measures, jointly monitor the achievement of the goal, clarify new goals and tasks based on the results obtained);
- activity-group criteria - the intensity of joint action, the emotional-psychological atmosphere in the team.

In modern conditions, the following were identified as the leading ideas of cooperative pedagogy in education: mutual action, creative cooperation; achieving success; individuality; self-education, self-improvement. Based on collaborative pedagogy, students also have the opportunity to develop communicative competence, work ethic, leadership, the ability to organize and analyze large-scale, clearly coherent materials, and the ability to supplement them in situations where information is insufficient.

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